

PEDAGOGICAL SKILL OF A MUSIC TEACHER AND ITS MAIN COMPONENTS

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Abstract: This article discusses the pedagogical skills of music teachers in the educational system and its main components. Also, the scientific theoretical basis of pedagogical skills and the theoretical analysis of formation are described.

Key words: Educational system, pedagogical skill, strategic technology, music teacher, evolutionary development, creative activity.

Introduction:

It is known that taking into account the evolutionary development of society's life, drastic changes in the content of education will not be implemented. This process is gradual and gradual. The teacher's musical pedagogic skill is improved in connection with the development of the educational content of science, technology, production and culture. At the current stage of the development of the society, the process of improving the musical and pedagogical skills of the teacher is taking place. This requires that the content of education should match the requirements of science and production. The conformity of the educational content to the requirements of science and production ensures the stabilization of the labor market and the cultural life of the society, and satisfies its need for qualified personnel. All of these ultimately help to solve the main problems of the society. It provides an opportunity for effective activity of science and production areas.

Improving the teacher's musical-pedagogical skills in the content of general secondary education requires the collection and generalization of several concepts. The problem of taking into account innovations in science and technology, technologies and production is one of the important tasks of improving the teacher's musical-pedagogical skills. Its solution, according to our research, serves to determine the possibilities of students to choose one or another field of science and production.

It is known that after the independence of our country, computers and information technologies were introduced into the educational process. This requires students to develop the skills of working with biotechnologies, technical tools, to understand the essence of microelectronic devices, and to familiarize them closely with the theoretical approaches of scientists in this direction. This, in turn, makes it possible to develop the labor market, master complex technologies, and fundamentally change the professional composition of the population. As a result of this, the nature of social work has changed, it has started to acquire more intellectual character, which changes the economic activity of the person, develops its material, technical and organizational basis. This makes the task of developing the technical base of the school, regular modernization of educational tools, and applying new forms of the educational process more urgent.

The introduction of the state educational standard in musical education, as well as in all educational subjects, allows full use of the national musical heritage. These are reflected in popular folk tunes and songs, creative activities of singers and musicians, and today's modern musical activities. Such opportunities of musical art serve as a unique and unrepeatable resource for the education of the new generation and their development. From time immemorial, education, pedagogy, and pedagogy of the East, including Uzbek music, and its excellent stylists, have been improved by the example of the tradition of teacher and student.

The state educational standards standardize the teaching of elementary basics of popular folk music pedagogy, works of professional music creators, music performers (composers, singers). Today, the content of general secondary education should serve for the future. It should be determined not only by considering the state and parameters of the socio-economic spheres surrounding us, but also by taking into account their future development. Today, it is one of the urgent tasks of a skilled music teacher to improve the lessons of music art and culture from a scientific and methodological point of view and to conduct them in accordance with the requirements of the time.

Based on this, all-round training of future personnel is a distinctive sign of pedagogical, technical-technological, professional education, learning new things based on practice, striving for knowledge, improving skills, qualifications, and skills. It is focused on uncovering the important issues of development, production and society. Based on the above considerations, taking into account the topicality of the topic today, it became the basis for choosing the subject of the research work as "Teacher's musical-pedagogical skills".

In order to become a true master of a profession, one must have natural abilities, certain physical and mental qualities. In order to effectively carry out the work of teaching and educating young people in pedagogic activities, to be worthy of the respect of parents and students, a person must have the ability, ability, skill, and interest. Every teacher must have pedagogical skills to work successfully. The owner of pedagogical skills achieves great results with little effort. Creativity will always be his partner. Pedagogical skills can only be found in people who are capable and talented in pedagogical work.

In order to have musical-pedagogical skills, one must first of all be capable, competent and able. Ability appears and develops in the process of activity. Ability is different from competence and competence. If competence and perseverance are considered the result of training and study, the place of talent in the development of ability is incomparable. It is only then that the mental quality called the faculty develops. In order for the pedagogical activity to be effective, the pedagogue should have the following types of abilities. Ability to know, ability to explain, ability to observe, ability to speak, ability to organize, ability to gain reputation, ability to see the future, ability to divide attention, etc.

The teacher's musical-pedagogical skill is very individual in its essence. The important vital role of every pedagogue is to be a master of his work. Master is expressed as very advanced, knowledgeable, or skillfully performing his work. Pedagogical skills of a music teacher can be seen in his work. First of all, a pedagogue should have a good understanding of the laws and mechanisms of the pedagogical process. In this sense, the generalized skills of the pedagogue and his pedagogical technique are of great importance.

Mastery is a special power. A real master is beautiful only during his work. Achieving musical-pedagogical skill is realized with certain personal qualities of the pedagogue.

Musical-pedagogical skill represents the development of pedagogical activity at a high level, acquisition of pedagogical techniques, as well as the personality of the pedagogue, his experience, civil and professional status.

The teacher's musical-pedagogical skill is understood as a bright manifestation of individuality in professional activity. The category of the teacher's musical-pedagogical skill characterizes the individuality of the person from the point of view of professional activity. In current studies, the uniqueness of musical-pedagogical skill is summarized in the following categories:

- performance skills;
- musical-pedagogical activities;
- creative activity;
- musical knowledge;
- musical style;
- innovative activity;
- pedagogical technology.

A pedagogue who is a skilled master of his work is a specialist who is highly cultured, has a deep knowledge of his subject, is able to analyze the relevant fields of science or art, and has mastered the methodology of education and training. If we understand this definition well and analyze its meaning, it will be possible to distinguish the following issues that are included in the content of the concept of pedagogical skill in this definition:

1. a high level of general culture and a high indicator of knowledge and intelligence;
2. has a wide and deep knowledge of the subject he is teaching;
3. to be armed with knowledge in the field of pedagogy, theory and methodology of music teaching, general and pedagogical psychology, to have good performance skills, to be able to use them freely and expertly in the experience of teaching and training work;
4. Perfect mastery of music teaching methodology.

The content of the teacher's musical-pedagogical skill can be divided into the following interrelated main parts:

1. musical-pedagogical humanitarian direction;
2. knowledge of music specialty;
3. musical-pedagogical ability;
4. musical - pedagogical technique (skill-talent).

Today's society requires initiative, creativity, and independent thinking from everyone in all spheres. The lesson is the main field of pedagogical creativity. The main pedagogical need of the teacher - to teach, to deliver - is realized in the lesson. Therefore, a correct, new approach to the organization of the educational process is needed.

In the course of the lesson, the pedagogue faces an important issue. Attracting students to learning is to move them forward. This attracts the pedagogue and students to (mutual) joint work. You should not be forced to teach for this. One of the visions of pedagogical cooperation is to remove the student's fear in the lesson, to make him more free and bold, to convince himself of his strength, to look at him as a person capable of serious creativity. The idea of a clear goal in the lesson. To work with these students in the spirit of cooperation, to set them a specific goal, to convince them of the complexity of this goal and to realize it - to form in them self-confidence and the ability to solve a specific, difficult problem.

The role of the lesson is important in the musical-pedagogical skill of the teacher. The lesson is such a center that every thought and action of the pedagogue revolves around this center and returns to it again. Each lesson makes its own unique contribution to the teaching process. The modern lesson is not limited to the methods and forms of teaching, but requires the implementation of educational and development goals, the realization of mutual interdependence in the activities of the pedagogue and the student.

The lesson requires creative pedagogical thinking and pedagogical skill from the pedagogue. The teacher's teaching tools are based on his creativity, versatile knowledge, love for students, and his activities. The success of a pedagogue in teaching depends on his theoretical and professional training. In the process of preparing a lesson, a pedagogue should regularly read psychological-pedagogical, methodical books, magazines and newspapers, use fiction and various films. In the process of teaching, the tools can be different. It depends on the specialty of the pedagogue, his curiosity, needs, intellectual activity. Of course, it is important to analyze the content of the studied material. The lesson consists of several factors. The main of these is the material adopted by the state pedagogy. The teacher should know the main directions of the curriculum. Each lesson should focus on 3 issues. These are:

1. Educational issues - forms the pedagogue's outlook on current issues and the environment. It cultivates the spirit of humanity and patriotism in them.
2. Issues that increase knowledge - include equipping students with knowledge, skills and abilities.
3. Knowledge issues - formation of students' ability to distinguish the main and important parts of the studied materials, to be independent in educational activities and thinking, to overcome difficulties in studying.

A skilled pedagogue takes into account the spirit and level of knowledge of students. It seems to some pedagogues that the educational material is understandable and does not require any special explanation.

Such pedagogues do not mean students, but themselves. A competent and experienced pedagogue can put himself in the place of a student. He works to explain the scientific-theoretical foundations of science to students. That's why he comes up with the character and form of the statement separately. A skillful pedagogue notices how the students learn the lesson material based on a number of signs and changes the way of presentation when necessary. Also, the pedagogue prepares the ground for students' literacy, taking into account the need for them to switch from rest to work, leave work, laziness, use the minimum level of time to eliminate their abilities. He does not start work until the appropriate situation arises.

Only if the teacher has high musical and pedagogical skills, manners and culture, he can be kind and generous to people, everyone respects him. A pedagogue should creatively study universal values and apply them to the educational process. At the same time, it is necessary to preserve and promote our nationality, our traditions that have passed the test of centuries, and our vital principles such as always living with faith, and to inculcate them in the hearts of students. The teacher's musical-pedagogical skill has a creative character according to its essence. It is known that creativity arises only when a person faces a problem.

Of course, a pedagogue should be demanding, kind, patient, calm and have faith in his profession. A pedagogue who loves a student with all his heart smiles more and frowns less. Along with imparting knowledge to the students, at the same time, he is able to transfer his

character to them, and he seems to be an example of humanity. Pedagogical-psychological theories are of great importance in the formation of a teacher's musical-pedagogical skills, because modern pedagogical technologies are about the activities of great people who have their own in the formation of our spirituality, about the demands placed on them. The theories about serve as the main source of formation of pedagogical skills. The use of scientific pedagogical information is important in improving pedagogical experiences.

A music teacher should be highly cultured, unfailingly devoted to his profession, possess advanced pedagogical thinking. He must have the ability of continuous professional and cultural development. He should have deep knowledge and skills in pedagogy, psychology, music teaching methodology, aesthetic theory, especially music teaching. In particular, it should embody the qualities of playing instruments, singing and music theory to the extent necessary for a music teacher's specialty.

A music teacher should be a master of pedagogic communication and have the ability to effectively use the methods of pedagogical influence in any situation. The experience of inquisitive, creative teachers and the new methods they have discovered are the main support and source of inspiration for the continuous development of music education. A music teacher, as an art intellectual, is the leader of musical educational activities in the school. Today's music teacher is a scientific thinker, a seeker of advanced experiences and a creator, and he should strive to discover new forms and methods of music education. It is necessary to connect and enrich the content of music education with the content of other subjects and everyday life.

Ensuring a high quality indicator of the implementation of the national program, improving the content of education on the basis of State educational standards. Monitoring at the school, district, city, republic level to determine whether the knowledge acquired by students meets these standards by supporting the State educational standards in the educational process in all academic subjects. works are being carried out.

As provided for in the national program, information provision of the educational process is developing on the basis of modern information technologies and computer networks. The publishing base of science and education has developed. Educational - methodical, scientific, innovative, modern technologies are perfected and applied to the educational process. It is known that the subject of didactics is teaching, learning, and the content of education. The three components involved in this are interconnected, and one of them cannot be neglected.

When we start learning or teaching, the question naturally arises as to what we want to learn or teach. Both teaching and learning and their final result depend on the content of education. Since it is accepted to master texts of different content in specific ways, how to teach it depends on its content, which depends on the one who organizes learning, that is, the teacher.

Conclusion:

In short, didactic thinking means to search for and determine the constant connections and relationships of learning, teaching and educational content. Therefore, pedagogical technology, didactic technology, educational technology are considered the most effective tools in the educational process. They are widely used in world pedagogical practice.

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